

LINGUISTIC CHARACTERISTICS OF RELIGIOUS TERMS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract: *This article reveals the lexical and etymological features of the oldest theonyms. Views on onomastics are stated. Theology in linguistics is interpreted as a new direction.*

Keywords: *theology, linguistics, onomastics, theonyms, religious texts, god.*

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Our use of language can tell our listener or reader a great deal about ourselves – in particular, about our regional origins, social background, level of education, occupation, age, sex, and personality. A major function of language is the expression of personal identity – the signaling of who we are and where we belong. What are you, in the eyes of society to which you belong? It is a complex and multi-faceted question. What kind of people use what kind of language on what kind of occasion? People acquire varying status as they participate in social structure; they belong to many social groups; and they perform a large variety of social roles. Adoption of a social role requires the learning of a completely different language or a variety of language. For instance, a knowledge of Latin is required in traditional Roman Catholic practice; a restricted Latin vocabulary was once prerequisite for doctors in the writing out of prescriptions; Latin may still be heard in some degree ceremonies. Latin was for centuries viewed as models of excellence because of the literature and thought which this language expressed and the study of modern languages is still influenced by the practices of generations of classical linguistic scholars.

On the other side, the Arabic language has without doubt served as a very effective medium for the communication of the message of Islam. It has also served as a means for preserving the cultural and religious heritage of Arabic-speaking and Muslim peoples. In this sense, the language has been extremely useful to the religion. However, in its role as the language of the Qur'an, Arabic has benefited enormously. Furthermore, the need for Muslims, whether native or non-native speakers of Arabic, to memorize and recite verses from the Qur'an in their daily worship, in every day prayers, has helped to keep the Arabic language alive. It was due to its association with Islam and the Qur'an that Arabic gained a good deal of prestige as the language of faith, a faith that was gaining more and more followers with each new day. The interest in the new faith brought with it interest in the language of that faith. It was under the banner of Islam that Arabic has influenced many languages.

Materials and methods. Theology in linguistics is one of the new directions of modern linguistics is considered the etymology of theonyms in Uzbek linguistics is deep and perfect it is considered one of the unexplored issues awaiting its own research. Uzbek collecting, grouping and studying linguistic features of theonyms remains one of the urgent problems of

nomenclature. Uzbek onomastics is extensive and multifaceted. Theonyms is one of the branches of onomastics and is the name of religious concepts. "Theonyms are a new direction of linguistics studying religious communication - gave impetus to the formation of theological linguistics. The term theolinguistics is English derived from the words theo - religion, god and linguistics - linguistics. So, Theolinguistics is a science that studies religious language". Theolinguistics is human religious' activity and is a science that studies its linguistic expression. The object of research is the linguistic expression of religious thought. In World Linguistics such a direction began to be conducted under the name of theological linguistics. This is the case at the moment early examples of research in world linguistics are David Crystal, Jean Pierre.

Practical and scientific by famous scientists such as Van Noppen and William Samarin Van Noppen brought the term "theolinguistics" to science entered. For the first time, he managed to compile a collection of articles called "Theolinguistics". To the issues of language and religion in world linguistics by the 21st century a dedicated encyclopedia was created. In the "Brief Encyclopedia of Language and Religion" created, religious concepts of peoples living in different parts of the world and related to language features are highlighted. This is about theological linguistics and its problems further increased the interest.

There is a lot to learn about religion and language in the East started earlier. Linguistic study of the Holy Qur'an in Arabic linguistics arose during. Religious linguistics in Uzbek linguistics E. Begmatov, N. Ulukov, T. Yuldashev, M. Umarho'jaev, M. Galieva, Sh. Sultonova Linguists such as Sh. Yusupova conducted scientific research. Theolinguistics is a linguistics that is developing in Uzbek linguistics one of the networks. "Religious Terms and Expressions" in Uzbek by M. Umarhojaev. He is famous as a scientist who created an explanatory dictionary. The fact that theonyms in Uzbek religious texts do not have an alternative in the translated language is used as is. A service to provide the religious spirit inherent in the text does. From this point of view, N.Ulukov includes theonyms in the exotic lexicon. According to Kazan linguist M.Kh. Bakirov, the world Borean theory exists in linguistics.

Results. According to him, Indian European, Afro-Asian, Kartvelian, Uralic and Altaic language families are genetically related. As a result of the erosion of the common ancestor language, language families are a number of related dialects divided into groups. According to the conclusion of the famous linguist N.S. Trubetsky according to which, initially, the Indo-European language family is formed. Later, Ural-Altay. As a result of contact with the Mediterranean Sea, the Caucasian language family was separated.

Then the Altaic language family was born. The Uzbek language in the history of linguistics was originally part of the Altaic language family. Later, the Turkic language family is separate. The structure and root system of Turkic languages is extremely resistant is considered the vocabulary system has also undergone little change compared to other languages. For example, the language of Orhun-Enasoy monuments is an example of the literary language of the 8th century. Many words from the language are widely used in the current Uzbek lexicon. Some sound changes occurred in the words. Another category of words

is from consumption came out. "God is very sweet and gentle: I have blood" ("(Blue) God is like that seems to say: I gave a khan»).

Ancient mythological theonyms are universal and parallel in different languages unites peoples. One of the most used theonyms in our article. Let's dwell on the theonym of God. The word "God" appeared 2500 years before Christ. In etymological dictionaries interpreted differently. For example, the Kazakh Turkologist K.M. Musaev is equally ancient "to rise" is formed by adding the suffix -ir to the verb ten explains. Yakut scientist N.K. Antonova means tang+ir - "morning person" says that it is used. But the etymological dictionary of the Uzbek language does not give the etymology of this word. has become synonymous with the onym. Even now, God is in communication processes theonym is actively used. In English, it is sometimes pronounced Allah or God without translation.

Conclusion. On the other hand, as we have already suggested, transliteration and translation are capable of great distortions of the form and content of Islamic concepts. In the long run, such distortions cannot be without effect upon the spiritual life of the speaker of the language in which they occur — because of the built-in human tendency to practice what one thinks, and to think what the majority of one's peers usually understand by the words in common use. Per contra, the alert Muslim who resists the conventions surrounding him and injects into them new vision and new spiritual sensitivities is not only a blessing to his own English speaking community, but a living example of Islamic loyalty to the language of the holy Qur'an. Insistence upon using and preservation of that language are acts of Islamic purism necessary for preservation of that Qur'anic revelation.

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